

Network in Eastern European Neolithic and Wetland Archaeology

Scientific Cooperation between Eastern Europe and Switzerland

Albert Hafner
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and Wetland Archaeology for the improvement of field techniques and
dating methods (NEENAWA)

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ted pile-dwelling settlement at Lake Ohrid, Ploča Michov Grad, North
Macedonia (photo: Marco Hostettler; University of Bern, 2017)

Photograph (back page): Underwater photograph of wooden piles at
Lake Ohrid, Ploča Michov Grad, North Macedonia (photo: Johannes
Reich; University of Bern, 2018)

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Part I: INTRODUCTION, FRAMEWORK

I.1 The NEENAWA Project

The “Network in Eastern European Neolithic and Wetland Archaeology for the improvement of field techniques and dating methods” (NEENAWA) was an Institutional Partnership (IP) project between four archaeological heritage management and research institutions in Switzerland, Russia, North Macedonia and Ukraine. Project partners were the Institute of Archaeological Sciences of the University of Bern (Switzerland), the Department of the Archaeology of Eastern Europe and Siberia at the State Hermitage Museum in Saint Petersburg (Russia), the Taras Shevchenko National University in Kyiv (Ukraine) and the Center for Prehistoric Research in Skopje (North Macedonia). The project was led by Prof. Dr. Albert Hafner of the University of Bern together with colleagues from the above-mentioned institutions and included activities between 2015 and 2018. The IP consortium consisted of eight members coming from the four concerned countries in an equal way. A good gender and age mix was given (three senior researchers, five junior researchers; five male, three female researchers):

Switzerland:

Prof. Dr. Albert Hafner, University of Bern, full professor for prehistoric archaeology and director, Institute of Archaeological Sciences and Oeschger Centre for Climate Change Research (OCCR).

Prof. Dr. Ebbe Nielsen, University of Bern, honorary professor Institute of Archaeological Sciences, member of the working group Palaeoecology and Oeschger Centre for Climate Change Research (OCCR), vice-director of the Cantonal Archaeology unit Lucerne.

North Macedonia:

Asst. Prof. Dr. Goce Naumov, Goce Delcev University, Stip, lecturer.

Valentina Todoroska BA, Archaeological Museum of Struga, underwater archaeologist in pile-dwelling sites.

Russia:

Prof. Dr. Andrey Mazurkevich, The State Hermitage Museum, senior scientific researcher, general curator of the Department of Archaeology of Eastern Europe and Siberia.

Dr. Ekaterina Dolbunova, The State Hermitage Museum, junior scientific researcher, curator of the Department of Archaeology of Eastern Europe and Siberia.

Ukraine:

Yana Morozova MA, Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, head of the university laboratory "Centre for Underwater Archaeology, Archaeological and Ethnological Research", archaeological heritage protection.

Prof. Dr. Pavlo Shydlovskiy, Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Department of Archaeology and Museum Studies, associate professor, lecturer and specialist in Palaeolithic and Neolithic archaeology.

Funding was provided by the SCOPES programme of the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF). The project was focused on the enhancement of scientific infrastructure and training of students and professionals dealing with prehistoric archaeology, especially the Neolithic and the settlements near lakes, rivers and marshes. Neolithic and Bronze Age wetland sites around the Alps (so called pile-dwellings, Pfahlbauten or palafittes in German/French) are of outstanding universal value (UNESCO-world heritage since 2011). Typical sites are located in lakes, rivers and bogs, dating between 5300 and 800 BC. Of common character is the perfect conservation of wood, textiles from plant fabrics and many other organic materials. Larger quantities of sub-fossilized wood, as in the peri-alpine sites, offer the possibility of high-precision dating by dendrochronology. Research in these wetland sites started in the mid-19th century. Through large scale rescue excavations since the 1970s and the evolution of underwater archaeology in the same period, Swiss archaeologists accumulated a thorough experience with these specific sites. Research in wetland sites is shared between cantonal institutions and universities and led to a worldwide unique accumulation of knowledge. Comparable sites exist outside of the Alpine area, but in much smaller quantities. Regions like Russia (small lakes in NW-Russia) and North Macedonia (medium to large size lakes in the border zones of North Macedonia, Albania and Greece) have a high scientific potential; rivers in Ukraine are supposed to have the same type of sites.

The general aims of the IP were to build up a scientific network in Neolithic and wetland archaeology and the transfer of knowledge from Switzerland, as one of the worldwide leading countries in this field, to the participating Eastern European (EE) countries. Further aims were to concentrate on an improvement of archaeological field techniques (mainly underwater archaeology/ documentation under water/diving security) and dating methods. Dendrochronology is by far the most precise dating method available, but this method is not yet applied in Russia, Macedonia and Ukraine. The combined application of locally developed dendrochronological calendars and radiocarbon dating is most promising. All EE-sites have the potential to give new insights on the process of the Neolithisation of Europe. In order to achieve these goals, joint activities, such as workshops, seminars, public lectures, field trips, diving courses and study weeks, were organised in the individual countries within framework of the NEENAWA project.

I.3 Output, Dissemination

Scientific publications

Dolbunova, E., Hafner, A., Nielsen, E., Mazurkevich, A., Dolbunova, E., Naumov, G., Morozova, Y., Shydlovskiy, P. (2015). NEENAWA: Network in Eastern European Neolithic and Wetland Archaeology: first steps. *The European Archaeologist* 46, 68-70.

Mazurkevich, A., Kulkova, M. A., Dolbunova, E. (eds.) (2016). *Radiocarbon Neolithic Chronology of Eastern Europe in the VII-III millennium B.C.* Smolensk.

Naumov, G. (ed.) (2016). *Prehistoric Wetlands and Lakes: bringing forward dendrochronology in archaeology.* Book of abstracts from NEENAWA conference in Ohrid. Skopje: Center for Prehistoric Research.

Terpylovskiy, R.V., Shydlovskiy, P.S. (eds.) (2017). *Human & Landscape : Prehistoric Archaeology of Eastern Europe.* Collection of scientific works. *Vita Antiqua* 9. Kyiv: Center for Paleoethnological Research. <https://doi.org/10.37098/VA-2017-9>

Hafner, A., Brunner, M., Laabs, J. (2017). *Archaeology in Switzerland: research from under water to high-altitude mountains.* *Vita Antiqua* 9, 16-37.

Shydlovskiy, P., Diachenko, A., Dolbunova, E., Hafner, A., Mazurkevich, A., Morozova, Y., Naumov, G., Todoroska, V. (2018). *Prehistoric Networks in Southern and Eastern Europe.* Collection of scientific works. *Vita Antiqua* 10. Kyiv.

Morozova, Y., Shydlovskiy, P. (2018). *STEP AHEAD: NEENAWA 2017 International Scientific Conference report.* *Vita Antiqua* 10, 192-211.

Academic events

Archaeological field-week “Prehistory and underwater archaeology in Russia. Methods, history and perspectives of underwater archaeology”, Serteya, Russia, 09-16.08.2015

International Scientific Conference “HUMAN & LANDSCAPE: Geographical approach in the Prehistoric Archaeology”, Kyiv, Ukraine, 03-05.02.2016
<http://vitaantiqua.org.ua/en/archives/200#more-200>
<http://vovkcenter.org.ua/en/2016-hl>

Archaeological workshop “Prehistoric Wetlands and Lakes: bringing forward dendrochronology in archaeology”, Skopje and Ohrid, North Macedonia, 11-17.05.2016
<http://www.neenawameeting.cip-cpr.org/pages/program.html>

Center for
Prehistoric Research

I.4 Center for Prehistoric Research

One of the major achievements of the NEENAWA project was the establishment of the Center for Prehistoric Research (CPR), the first organization of archeologists in North Macedonia entirely focused on prehistory and wetland archaeology. The lack of the particular study of tell sites in wetlands and pile dwellings in Macedonian archaeology revealed a necessity for a more scientifically based implementation of current archaeological methods and consequently a group of archaeologists that will incorporate such principles in their research and promote them in North Macedonia. Therefore, with the support of the SNSF, the project group succeeded to make a significant step forward in improving the knowledge on prehistory and wetland archaeology by organizing courses, lectures, conferences and workshops, and sending students and professionals to broaden their scientific horizons in Switzerland, Russia and Ukraine. Gradually, CPR became involved in many other projects and established collaborations with institutions from Serbia, Slovenia, Czech Republic, Poland, Spain, Switzerland, Germany, Italy and Russia. These collaborations contribute to a further thorough research of cultural heritage associated with wetlands and lakesides and to the promotion of archaeological science in North Macedonia.

The Center for Prehistoric Research is dedicated to the study and presentation of all prehistoric periods in the Balkans and North Macedonia in particular. Considering the rich cultural heritage from this period, CPR's primary goal is to enable a thorough understanding of life of prehistoric communities while applying numerous scientific methods. CPR's members are archaeologists who study different aspects of the Paleolithic, Neolithic, Chalcolithic, Bronze Age and Iron Age period. Within their activities, archaeological sites are being studied and presented, as are the material culture, chronology and the geographical features of prehistory, so they could be interpreted applying the current theoretical models. Apart from the research activities, CPR organizes scientific round tables, workshops, lectures and conferences that actualize the problems of prehistoric archaeology. Moreover, CPR publishes editions that present the latest knowledge regarding the prehistoric cultural heritage in North Macedonia.

CPR cooperates with several domestic and international institutions and creates a platform for a future networking in projects that will thoroughly examine and present the prehistoric period. Within these cooperations students and young professionals are being trained through inclusion in field research, lab analyses, expert publications and public scientific events. As a result of these activities, CPR significantly impacts the application of new scientific approaches and ethical norms in the Macedonian archaeology. Thus, by presenting the cultural heritage through research, scientific debates and publications, CPR has a direct influence over the popularization of prehistory and the protection of sites and material culture from this period. CPR's aim is to enhance the cooperation among experts and institutions that will strengthen the scientific ethics and the research methods applied in prehistoric archaeology.

Lately, CPR has been involved in the excavation of two tells and one pile-dwelling; geomagnetic scanning of ten settlements and survey of about hundred archaeological sites. Reports and theoretical scientific articles regarding all these activities were published in Macedonian and in international journals and edited books. Moreover, the aforementioned research encompassed digital topographic measurements and 3D site modeling. Besides field work, radiocarbon, zooarchaeological, archaeobotanical and lithic use-ware analyses were being made with the collaborators from various countries, to be followed by isotopic, paleodemographic, anthropological and geological analyses, as well as analysis of lipids found on vessels.

Besides the individual cabinet research of neolithization, ceramography, semiotics, human presentations, funerary archaeology and the hominid evolution, through international cooperation CPR members also perform a photogrammetric 3D documenting of archaeological finds and architecture. These results were presented at two exhibitions in Serbia and Italy, where CPR was invited to present the prehistoric figurative art as well.

As previously mentioned, CPR also organizes lectures and conferences. The conference entitled 'Neolithic in Macedonia' had five editions so far, while the event 'Prehistoric Wetlands and Lakes' lasted a week and consisted of a conference, lectures, workshops and diving. Numerous lectures of distinguished European archaeologists were organized within educational activities, but also CPR members held lectures at the universities of Bern, Ljubljana, Vilnius, Modena, Kiev, Koper, Zurich and the Hermitage Museum in Saint Petersburg. Moreover, CPR members held seminars on Macedonian prehistory for Swiss and Slovenian students; the field research in Pelagonia also encompasses a training of Czech and Swiss students. Macedonian students had the opportunity to get acquainted with new archaeological methods in Switzerland, Russia and Ukraine, so they could implement their latest experience in their future scientific work. A prestigious European course for scientific diving was also organized, which provided licenses for underwater archaeology for participants from Macedonia and abroad.

Publishing is one of CPR regular activities, resulting in five publications so far. The edited book 'Neolithic in Macedonia' was published in five volumes and composes of articles presented at the conferences with the same name. The conference 'Prehistoric Wetlands and Lakes' resulted in publication of a leaflet with abstracts. In 2017, CPR published two monographs: (a) Macedonian bronzes by Nikos Čausidis and (b) Grnčarica by Darko Stojanovski, both significant contributions to the insight of Neolithic and Iron Age in Macedonia and the Balkans. Upon an invitation of the German Archaeological Institute, there was an exchange of publications focused on prehistory, so numerous Macedonian editions can now be found in their libraries, but also rare European magazines, journals and monographs are to be found in the library of CPR.

All activities have been successfully performed due to the excellent cooperation with the Archaeological Museum of Macedonia and the museums in Prilep, Bitola, Ohrid, Skopje and Štip, as well as due to the research performed with the Institute of Old Slavic Culture in Prilep, the Universities of Bern and Basel, BioSense Institute, Hermitage Museum, University of South Bohemia, Principat Krakow, University of Kiev, Spanish National Research Council, Free University of Berlin, Archaeological Museum of Udine and the German Archaeological Institute. Due to the collaboration with these institutions, there is much more thorough insight of the Macedonian prehistory that opens completely new scientific horizons.

CPR continues with the intense activities in all aspects, i.e. research, publication and education. Lectures and use-wear analyses are commenced with the colleagues from the Spanish National Research Council in several Macedonian museums and also the trainings in Macedonia and in Switzerland continue, as well as the organization of lectures and conferences, publication of a monograph and an edited book, participation at international conferences, giving guest lectures, but also prospection, geomagnetic scanning and excavation of prehistoric sites in the regions of Pelagonia and Ohrid, followed by analyses of vessels, figurines, tools, animal, human and organic remains with our collaborators from the aforementioned Macedonian and European museums and universities. CPR members are convinced that fruitful research will continue in the following years that will provide a plethora of new information regarding prehistory in Macedonia.

Yana Morozova, Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv

I.5 Centre for Underwater Archaeology

There is only one educational organization which combines both research and educational programmes on underwater archaeology in Ukraine: the Centre for Underwater Archaeology (CUA). The Centre was founded within the National Taras Shevchenko University of Kyiv in 1991. It is a research and educational university unit that focuses mainly on nautical archaeology throughout the Black Sea region and underwater archaeology in Ukraine in particular. The main aim of the CUA is to involve students, amateurs, sport divers and members of the general public in maritime archaeological field excavations and surveys, as well as educate them regarding this fascinating field and the preservation of underwater resources. Here they can study theory, methodology and the techniques of underwater archaeology, and acquire practical experience during summer excavations.

The Centre is currently carrying out its overview learning and training programmes for first year students, as well as developing a master's curriculum, which is a part of the general master's course in archaeology at the Department of Archaeology and Museum Studies. In addition, lectures on underwater archaeology are given to all interested members of the general public – amateur and professional divers alike. After attending the theoretical portion of the programme, they can actively participate in underwater archaeological expeditions carried out by the Centre. The expeditions are a very important part of the educational programme. While participating, the students who attended prior preparatory lectures and training sessions can implement their knowledge and practice their skills in a hands-on environment. For those participants who do not have a diving certification, attending the practical and theoretical classes provided by CMAS certified dive instructors is an excellent opportunity to obtain one.

The Centre works in close cooperation with the scientific committee of CMAS and the Ukrainian Federation of Underwater Sport and Underwater Activities.

Another significant undertaking of the Centre is the Underwater Archaeology Summer Field School. The field school participants learn how to excavate underwater and how to handle, preserve and record artifacts in the field. Students learn the practical aspects of underwater archaeology by taking part in the underwater excavation of the shipwrecks. All activities are held in shallow water under the supervision of professional underwater archaeologists and dive masters. Students are given lectures and are taken on excursions to various places of Ukraine.

Further information: <https://www.facebook.com/CUAKNU/>

I.6 Th. Vovk Center for Paleoethnological Research

The “Th. Vovk Center for Paleoethnological Research” is a non-governmental organization, founded in 2015. It groups young researchers: students, alumni and young scientists who have gathered together for solving scientific, education and heritage protection problems in contemporary archaeological, anthropological, and ethnological research and other adjacent disciplines. Young researchers are engaged in interdisciplinary investigations of human collectives’ activities and how they connected to the natural and cultural environment in the past. The Center is affiliated with the Department of Archaeology and Museum Studies of Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Ukraine.

Membership in the Center can be only voluntary and individual. According to the regulations, that young scientist can be a person up to 35 years of age. Statutes foresee that members of the Center above 35 years of age can be scientific consultants, if they have considerable scientific achievements.

The main tasks of the Center’s activity are archaeological research of prehistoric sites on the territory of Ukraine, popularization of the scientific results, preservation and protection of the cultural and natural heritage. Also, the Center strives to represent Ukrainian culture and nature, and to integrate Ukrainian social studies worldwide.

Tasks which the Center sets itself:

- Overcoming segregation in modern science, which is mirrored in the official institutions, and because of the high specialization research is becoming increasingly isolated from society. Because of this, paleoethnology provides integrated approaches to the study of historical events using the methods of natural sciences and humanities.
- Carry out complex studies of ancient societies to demonstrate relationships between human communities themselves and with the environment at different stages of historical development. Development of new ideas and views on modern society through the study of the history of its formation.
- Following the principles of research ethics in studies, which provides a complete rejection of dogmatism, indoctrination, authoritarianism and falsification of facts. Instead, in priority are the principles of teamwork, universalism, unselfishness and verification of the findings.
- Be actively involved in the process of protection of cultural and natural heritage in the territory of Ukraine through direct participation and in cooperation with state administration, scientific and other non-governmental organizations.
- Exchange the experience in field and laboratory research with colleagues from abroad; use international experience in the field of protection of cultural and nature heritage;
- Organizational joining the European and world organizations, whose purpose is the study and protection of monuments of prehistoric culture and environment.

Its members actively participate in field research on archaeological sites and reconstruction of living activities of prehistoric societies in their environmental context. The worldwide-known Mezhyrich site, an Upper-Paleolithic settlement of mammoth hunters, is one of the most interesting sites which the members of the Center have been investigating for a long period.

They also investigate archaeological sites of the Neolithic and Trypillya archaeological cultures. Such archaeological sites of the Neolithic - Bronze Age in the territory of Eastern Europe are of great interest for scientists in the context of the spread of agriculture and new technologies in the early Holocene. Already amazing discoveries have been made in the Middle Dnieper and Dniester

basins, and exploration goes on. Every year the Center's specialists carry out investigations of prehistoric sites of the Dniester river valley – Bernashivka, Vasylivka, and Ozheve. These sites demonstrate different stages of development of the Trypillian-Cucuteni cultural unity. The Center is involved in international cooperation and exchange of experiences in field and laboratory research. Its members organize exhibitions, take part in the international conferences with presentations, and work with their colleagues from abroad on the archaeological collections and data. Archaeologists and students from the Center participate in international projects and programs, and seek any good opportunity to gain and share knowledge in the field of protection and study of cultural heritage in future projects.

Recent activities of the Center are:

- organizing the exhibition “Ukrainian-French cooperation in the investigation of the Palaeolithic sites of Middle Dnieper region”,
- publishing a book “Prehistoric archaeology of Lower Desna region”,
- providing a course of video lectures “Popular Anthropology” etc.

Since 2016, the Center is founder and publisher of the periodical scientific journal VITA ANTIQUA.

More information:

<http://vovkcenter.org.ua/en/main/>

<http://vitaantiqua.org.ua>

<https://www.facebook.com/th.vovk.center>

Part III: KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER, SCIENTIFIC EXCHANGE 2015–2018

Pavlo Shydlovskiy, Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv,
Ekaterina Dolbunova, The State Hermitage Museum, Saint Petersburg

III.7 International Open Workshop: Socio-Environmental Dynamics over the Last 12,000 Years: The Creation of Landscapes V

Participants of NEENAWA project took part in the International Open Workshop “Socio-Environmental Dynamics over the Last 12,000 Years: The Creation of Landscapes V”, organised by the Graduate School “Human Development in Landscapes” at Kiel University, between 20 and 24 March 2017. They were particularly engaged in the session “Lakescapes and Seascapes of Neolithic and Bronze Age societies” (Session 18). The session was devoted to investigations into the development of lakeside and seaside sites that played a significant part in the subsistence economy, as well as in the communication/interaction and social developments of prehistoric people. Beside the traditional known wetland sites, especially the last decade brought to attention new discoveries of lake and sea sites. The comprehension of their relevance to European prehistory, and their occurrence in other European areas than those known before, is changing our entire view of prehistoric settlement patterns. To comprehend this development and the importance of waterscapes as active compounds in sustaining livelihoods, as well as the relevance of seaside and lakeside sites in the European prehistory, various matters need to be tackled. This session aimed at bringing together contributors from different fields to put side by side and discuss evidence from various regions in Europe and comparable situations from other continents. Among the points to be brought into discussion, are the diverse methods and techniques proposed for exploring the lakeside and seaside sites.

Albert Hafner was invited as a keynote lecturer in the above mentioned session. In addition, two papers were represented by Russian team of the NEENAWA project entitled:

A. Mazurkevich, E. Dolbunova, P. Kittel, E. Kazalov: Lacustrine pile-dwellings of the 4th-3rd mill BC: particularities of landscape, economy and culture (NW Russia).

E. Dolbunova, A. Mazurkevich, A. Tsybrii, V. Tsybrii, M. Sablin: Using waterscapes in Early Neolithic: new investigations in the southern Russia (site Rakushechny Yar).

Goce Naumov, Goce Delcev University, Stip,
Pavlo Shydlovskiy, Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv

III.8 Neolithic Seminar at the University of Bern

A significant component of NEENAWA project was the sharing of knowledge among mutually unfamiliar academic environments. As part of this process realized on various occasions during the project, also a Neolithic Seminar was initiated that intended to introduce Swiss students to the prehistory of an area that is not regularly included in their curriculum. The Seminar took place from 23 to 30 May 2017 at the Institute of Archaeological Sciences of the University of Bern and was focused on the Neolithic of East and Southeast Europe (i.e. the Balkans) where representatives of Taras Shevchenko University (fig. 1) and the Center for Prehistoric Research (fig. 2) gave lectures and assisted students in their work. The working language was English.

The Macedonian project partner (fig. 2) guided the students in their research of the Neolithic Balkans and chronology, pottery, identity, burials and human representations in particular. Prior to their final presentations in May consultation and preparation of their seminar works took place (fig. 3, 4). Students were focused on the Early Neolithic chronology of the Balkans and calibration of available dates, pottery production and their relationship with identity, as well as on research on intramural burials, anthropomorphic figurines and house models in Macedonia. For that purpose, a bibliography was provided for them which they used with particular interest in detail.

The second part of the seminar was devoted to the topic "Cucuteni-Trypillia settlements: material culture, chronology and space". The introductory lecture was given by the assistant professor of the Department of Archeology and Museology, Pavlo Shydlovskiy (fig. 5), followed by lectures from both Ukrainian as well as Swiss students. At the end of each lecture and especially after the seminar, there were lively discussions between lecturers (fig. 6) and students which resulted in valuable input for each side.

Students were dedicated in their work and demonstrated meticulous curiosity in exploring a new area of archaeological research and a new region. In matter of few months they prepared their written work with thorough text and images consisted of graphs as well. This confirms their analytical approach and willingness to understand systematically the Neolithic of the Eastern Europe and the subject areas they have chosen. Their seminar work was finalized with presentations in front of students and professors. During their presentations they clearly elaborated the results, self-confidently demonstrating the knowledge they obtained. In general, the seminar work was very successful and proved that Swiss students are talented and dedicated individuals that profoundly entered into a new sphere of archaeological research i.e. the Neolithic of Eastern Europe.

In addition, the Macedonian and Ukrainian project partners had the opportunity to use the well-equipped library of the Institute of Archaeological Sciences (fig. 7) and to visit museums in the cities of Bern and Geneva.

Fig. 1: Ukrainian researchers Ivan Radomskyi, Alyona Tron-Radomskaya and Pavlo Shydlovskiy in front of the Institute of Archaeological Sciences at the University of Bern (photo: Pavlo Shydlovskiy)

Fig. 2: Goce Naumov during his lecture on the Neolithic Balkans (photo: Pavlo Shydlovskiy)

Fig. 3: Swiss student Corina Gottardi giving a lecture on "Human Representations and Burials of the First Farmers" (photo: Goce Naumov)

Fig. 4: Swiss student Lea Emmenegger giving a lecture on "The Process of the Neolithization in the Balkans" (photo: Goce Naumov)

Fig. 5: Pavlo Shydlovskiy during his lecture on Cucuteni-Trypillia settlements (photo: Pavlo Shydlovskiy)

Fig. 6: Discussion between Albert Hafner and Pavlo Shydlovskiy (photo: Pavlo Shydlovskiy)

Fig. 7: Ivan Radomsky in the library of the Institute of Archaeological Sciences (photo: Pavlo Shydlovskiy)

The Bern Working Papers on Prehistoric Archaeology (ISSN 2297- 8607) is an online series dedicated to innovative research ideas and research findings on prehistoric societies. Focussing on inter- and transdisciplinary methodologies, the series is seeking to enrich discussion and collaboration between scholars of different disciplines and institutions in countries around Europe. The working papers form part of research groups based at the division of Prehistory, Institute of Archaeological Sciences (University of Bern).
Papers in English or German language from other research groups are also welcome.

Submission of proposals to
albert.hafner@iaw.unibe.ch

Die Berner Arbeitspapiere zur Prähistorischen Archäologie (ISSN 2297- 8607) sind eine Online-Schriftenreihe, die innovativen Forschungsansätzen zu prähistorischen Gesellschaften gewidmet ist. Im Fokus stehen inter- und transdisziplinäre methodologische Ansätze. Die Serie soll Austausch und Zusammenarbeit von Forschenden aus unterschiedlichen Disziplinen und Institutionen fördern, die in verschiedenen Ländern tätig sind. Die Arbeitspapiere sind Teil der Forschungsgruppen, welche bei der Abteilung für Prähistorische Archäologie am Institut für Archäologische Wissenschaften (Universität Bern) angesiedelt sind.
Beiträge in deutscher oder englischer Sprache von anderen Forschungsgruppen sind ebenfalls willkommen.

Einreichung von Beitragsvorschlägen bei
albert.hafner@iaw.unibe.ch

The “Network in Eastern European Neolithic and Wetland Archaeology for the improvement of field techniques and dating methods” (NEENAWA) was an Institutional Partnership between archaeological institutions in North Macedonia, Russia, Ukraine and Switzerland, funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF). The project focused on the enhancement of scientific infrastructure and training of students and professionals dealing with Neolithic settlements near lakes, rivers and marshes.

The aim of this book is to document the activities performed during and arising from this project between 2015 and 2020. Activity and experience reports as well as scientific case studies keep record of the various actions and events that took place in the partner countries. They also witness to the scientific and structural development of wetland and underwater archaeology in Eastern Europe.

